

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Annotation: This thesis explores the transformative role of artificial intelligence (AI) in modern education, highlighting its numerous advantages. AI has the potential to revolutionize educational practices through personalized learning experiences, intelligent tutoring systems, enhanced engagement and motivation, and predictive analytics. The thesis discusses how AI can provide tailored instruction, adaptive assessments, and 24/7 availability of intelligent tutors, thereby improving student outcomes. It also covers the benefits of gamification and interactive content in keeping students engaged and motivated. Additionally, the thesis examines the role of AI in predictive analytics and early intervention, enabling educators to identify at-risk students and provide targeted support. The efficiency and consistency brought by automated grading and feedback systems are discussed, along with the enhanced accessibility AI offers for students with disabilities. Data-driven insights for educators, improved teacher support, and optimized curriculum development are further explored as key advantages of AI in education.

The thesis concludes by emphasizing the cost-effectiveness of AI implementation in educational institutions, which can lead to resource optimization and long-term savings. By leveraging AI's capabilities, education systems can create more effective, inclusive, and adaptive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students, ultimately enhancing cognitive development and overall academic achievement.

Key words: artificial intelligence, personalized learning experiences, achievements, influence, personalized learning, intelligent tutoring systems, academic achievements.

Artificial intelligence (AI) exists in our lives and in modern times developing with efficiency. The beginning of artificial intelligence 1956 It originates from summer scientific research in informatics at Dartmouth. Today artificial intelligence work in the day in the investigation of cancer of the police, aircraft in reducing the risk of collision, in the development of autonomous vehicles and so on. Robots equipped with artificial intelligence from human surgeons in sewing cuts lost; perform search and rescue missions; children, the

elderly and in the hospital ensuring patient care; fraud to master card firms help with identification. Artificial intelligence technology over the past twenty years applied in education. Intellectual Tutoring Systems (IRTS) all major artificial intelligence topics (e.g., data representation, machine learning, language, planning, reasoning, explanation) covers and therefore systems to formalize and experiment with theories of psychological characteristics formed a motivational test site. Their activities artificial intelligence in education has been applied in many fields such as physics, programming, essay writing, and reading, because the development of educational systems is the most basic typical Artificial in the academic field intelligence applications include data imaging, Intelligent Tutoring, language process, and autonomous includes agents. Artificial intelligence in education students for decades created a strong educational environment and positive interactive experiences for. The rapid development of technologies such as artificial intelligence has accelerated all areas in addition to education.

Artificial intelligence is changing the teaching process in education.

Since the beginning of education, teaching strategies as well as the relationship between students and teachers has developed significantly. Artificial intelligence nowadays the world across instructional strategies and to manage additional effective outcomes has become a successful structure. This change is mainly a constant of technology depends on the effect. Behind the continuous technological advancement, we are witnessing a paradigm shift in the way we teach. Teachers and students. The communication between artificial intelligence is dynamic and it is impossible to make this communication permanent where it is convenient and quite high. Artificial intelligence is a plus created an educational cooperative.

How is artificial intelligence currently being used in education?

Microsoft and McKinsey's Canada, Singapore, UK and This is the report of more than 2000 students and 2000 teachers from America shows that artificial intelligence is already helping teachers and schools to learn and innovative ways to help schools understand how to make sense is presenting. their students are developing, as well as the rapid, allows for personalized, targeted continuity.

The role of artificial intelligence in education

1. Artificial intelligence can be used for basic activities in education, such as assessment can automate. Artificial intelligence will never replace human assessment Although not ready, it is very closed. At the moment, almost all types

of academics are one multiple alternative tests and may change the assessment to fill the gap and automated grading of student writing may not be far behind.

2. Students get additional help from artificial intelligence teachers possible These programs teach students the basics, but only so far not ideal for learning higher order thinking and creative thinking, it's something real-world teachers still need to facilitate. However, these AI tutors will try these things in the future should not exclude the possibility of being able to see.

3. AI-based software can provide useful feedback to students and teachers. Not only can AI help academics and students create courses tailored to their preferences, however, it can give everyone feedback on the overall success of the course. These types of AI systems help students support themselves and helps professors look for areas to improve teaching.

4. The role of teachers can change. Teachers in education

There will always be work for, but what is this role and what does it mean, because smart new technologies such as computing systems may change. As mentioned above As we have seen, artificial intelligence can take on tasks such as assessment,

helping students improve their learning and even actual tutoring can be replaced.

5. AI-powered data of schools can change how they find, teach and support students. Intelligent data collection controlled by intelligent computer systems are already making changes to their interactions with prospective students. From recruiting to helping students choose the most effective courses to give intellectual computer systems to the students of the faculty helps to adapt to their needs and goals.

There are different areas where artificial intelligence affects.

1. Artificial intelligence in marketing: a study of customer data .It is used to predict the behavior of people and for sellers helps easy segmentation.

2. Artificial intelligence in banking: a fast-growing approach, with manybank credit card fraud detection, anomaly detection and electronic To artificial intelligence to support clients through a Virtual assistant based methods are used.

3. Finance is here to identify market patterns in a very short time uses an approach. These machines store past data samples checks and predicts future feedback on the data.

4. Artificial intelligence in agriculture: some automation approaches use farmers to get a good harvest of their crops and weed them helps protect.

5. Identification and simulation of complex human conditions in health care and it uses complex algorithms to pre-supply drugs.
6. Creating flexible and intelligent behavior for players in the game to.
7. Processing and processing data of this scale in the study of the universe is the best way to work. This artificial intelligence is NASA's next Used for the Mars 2020 mission.
8. Artificial intelligence in autonomous vehicles: artificial intelligence system transport transport to produce control signals that drive the vehicle tools collect data from radars, cameras, GPS and cloud services.
9. AI in Chat bots: Virtual help today everyone like Siri, Alexa, Cotona widely used in one house. It includes home appliance control, book booths, food order, etc.k. can be used for.
10. Artificial intelligence in artificial creation: artificial as social platforms like Facebook creativity. Artificial intelligence machine for face recognition and automatic touch uses learning and deep learning algorithm methods, our interests

designing a ribbon based on hate speech and identifying negative content

Students should be prepared to work with artificial intelligence systems in the future. But most young people, despite being students, are not familiar with digital technologies.

remain uninformed, so they need to be digitally literate. Artificial intelligence in education

Addition should take education to a new level, but the world must also be prepared to face the challenges posed by artificial intelligence.

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